

Switchgrass Best Management Practices for Biofuel Production

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Executive Summary

Switchgrass is a perennial C₄ grass native to North America and broadly adaptable across the U.S. Its high productivity, low input requirements, and ability to deliver significant ecosystem services benefits, including carbon sequestration, soil conservation, and wildlife habitat, make it well-suited for cultivation on marginal lands. Achieving the U.S. Department of Energy’s projected potential of 1 billion dry tons of biomass annually by 2050 – with switchgrass contributing up to 230 million tons – will require a transition to large-scale, commercial production¹. This technical guide was developed to provide decision-makers with current best management practices (BMPs) for establishing, managing, and harvesting bioenergy switchgrass at scale on marginal lands across the U.S. Midwest and Great Plains. Drawing extensively on previous field research and insights from the five-year *'Next-Generation Feedstocks for the Emerging Bioeconomy'* project – funded by the U.S. Department of Energy’s Bioenergy Technologies Office – this guide provides practical strategies for scaling up switchgrass production to meet the demands of the growing bioeconomy. The guide distills research-based insights into actionable recommendations, organized into the following thematic areas:

Agronomic Management

Successful large-scale deployment of switchgrass requires optimized management strategies, including:

- **Variety Selection:** Lowland varieties (Kanlow, Independence, Mt. Airy, and Cedar Creek) and a hybrid, Liberty, offer high yield potential in mid- and southern latitudes. Upland varieties

¹ US DOE (2024). “2023 Billion-Ton Report”.
<https://www.energy.gov/eere/bioenergy/2023-billion-ton-report-assessment-us-renewable-carbon-resources>

(Shawnee, Cave-In-Rock, Sunburst, and Carthage) are better suited for mid- to northern U.S. latitudes.

- **Establishment Practices:** Switchgrass grows well on a variety of soils, with best results on well-drained, moderately fine-textured soils (pH 5.5-7.0). Planting should occur from mid-April to early June, with seeds placed ¼ to ½ inch deep. No-till seeding into soybean stubble is preferred; conventional tillage requires a firm, packed seedbed. Use drills with depth bands and closing wheels; avoid broadcast seeding due to poor depth control.
- **Weed Control:** Weed management strategies should consider previous land use, ground conditions, soil fertility, planting methods, and planting date. A combination of pre- and post-emergence herbicides – including atrazine, quinclorac, and 2,4-D is recommended, particularly during the first two establishment years².
- **Fertilization:** Apply no nitrogen (N) in the establishment year to reduce weed pressure. From year two onward, apply 10-15 lbs (5-7 kg) of N per ton of biomass removed if harvesting after a killing frost. Adjust rates based on soil N and mineralization estimates from soil tests.
- **Harvest:** Switchgrass should be harvested once annually after a killing frost to enhance nutrient translocation and improve feedstock quality. The target stubble height is 4-6 inches, and biomass should be baled with a moisture content below 20% to prevent spoilage.

Economic Viability

Switchgrass could be more profitable than corn and soybean on marginal lands, with yields around 4.66 tons/acre (10.45 Mg/ha) and the farmgate

² Consult herbicide labels, regulations, restrictions, and licensing requirements specific to your state prior to application, as rules vary regionally.

price of \$80/ton. Depending on biomass yield, the annual production costs, including annualized establishment cost, average \$138/acre/year (\$340/ha/year) in Illinois and \$119/acre/year (\$294/ha/year) in Iowa with 50 lbs N/acre (56 kg N/ha) fertilization. Profit margins are estimated at \$156/acre/year (\$385/ha/year) for Independence in Illinois and \$142/acre/year (\$350/ha/year) for Liberty in Iowa and Nebraska, assuming the farmer owns the land. Advanced bioenergy cultivars show strong economic performance compared to forage-type cultivars.

Environmental and Ecosystem Benefits

Switchgrass offers substantial ecosystem services:

- **Carbon Sequestration:** Switchgrass increases soil carbon at rates of 1.01-2.8 Mg C/ha/year. Belowground (root) biomass carbon can accumulate up to ~2 Mg C/ha/year of cultivation.
- **Erosion Control:** Switchgrass's perennial root system stabilizes soil, protecting against wind and water erosion on fragile lands.
- **Reduced Emissions and Leaching:** Switchgrass requires less fertilizer than annual crops, resulting in lower nitrous oxide emissions and up to 80% reduction in nitrate leaching compared to corn in mature stands.
- **Wildlife Habitat and Pollinator Support:** Switchgrass fields provide critical spring and summer habitat for grassland birds and pollinators, supporting species such as the Common Yellowthroat, Dickcissel, Grasshopper Sparrow, and Sedge Wren more frequently than corn fields. They also support greater insect and pollinator diversity – including bees, flies, beetles, and butterflies – compared to corn fields.

Outlook and Policy Implications

Switchgrass is a productive, environmentally beneficial, and economically viable option, but its broader adoption is limited by market and

infrastructure gaps. Policy support is needed to incentivize both farmers and biorefineries by recognizing environmental benefits and ensuring long-term feedstock supply chains.

Introduction

Switchgrass (*Panicum virgatum* L.) is a perennial warm-season (C₄) grass that is native to the tallgrass prairies of North America. It is broadly adapted to regions below 55°N latitude, spanning from Canada to northern Mexico. Historically, switchgrass has grown alongside other key prairie species such as big bluestem, Indiangrass, sideoats grama, little bluestem, eastern gamagrass, and various forbs (e.g., sunflowers, gayfeather, prairie clover, and prairie coneflower).

As the U.S. advances its renewable bioeconomy, the inherent traits and well-documented research history of switchgrass make it highly suitable for large-scale feedstock production across diverse agro-ecoregions. Its appeal as a bioenergy crop stems from its proven long-term (>10 years) productivity in multiple environments, adaptability to marginal cropland, low water and nutrient requirements, ease of establishment and management, compatibility with conventional haying equipment, high biomass yields, and a favorable chemical profile suitable for conversion technologies.

Switchgrass offers multiple environmental benefits, including soil carbon sequestration, reduced nutrient losses and soil erosion, and mitigation of greenhouse gas emissions. In line with national energy goals, the U.S. Department of Energy (US DOE), in collaboration with other federal agencies, has set targets to produce 3 billion gallons of sustainable aviation fuel (SAF) annually by 2030 and 35 billion gallons by 2050³. Meeting the 2050 target will require 400 biorefineries processing 1 billion dry tons of biomass and/or gaseous carbon dioxide feedstock annually. About 345 million of the 1-billion dry-ton biomass annual supply is

³ US DOE (2022). “Sustainable Aviation Fuel Grand Challenge”.
<https://www.energy.gov/eere/bioenergy/sustainable-aviation-fuel-grand-challenge>

projected to come from herbaceous perennial energy crops, with switchgrass contributing 230 million dry tons¹.

Marginal land, accounting for about 9% of current cropland, will be an important resource for realizing biomass production targets. Meeting these targets will require specialized expertise in variety selection, stand establishment, fertilization, weed control, and harvest management.

Variety Selection

For optimal performance, growers should select switchgrass varieties based on ecotype differences, as each is adapted to specific geographic regions. The two primary ecotypes are **upland** and **lowland**. Upland ecotypes are finer-stemmed, shorter (typically 5-6 feet tall), more cold-tolerant, and sod-forming, making them better suited to the mid and northern U.S. latitudes and ideal for grazing systems. Lowland ecotypes are tall, reaching up to 6-7 feet, and are bunch-forming grasses. Generally, lowland varieties have a later heading date and are well adapted to wetter soils. They produce taller plants with fewer but thicker tillers than upland types, contributing to higher biomass yields and making them more suitable for southern and mid-latitudes. Common lowland switchgrass varieties include Kanlow, Liberty (a hybrid between upland and lowland), Independence, Mt. Airy, and Cedar Creek. Upland varieties include Shawnee, Cave-In-Rock, Sunburst, Carthage, and Shelter (Table 1).

Generally, switchgrass cultivars should not be planted more than one USDA hardiness zone north or south of their region of origin. Exceeding this adaptation range can result in poor winter survival and substantial biomass yield losses. Lowland cultivars are less cold-hardy and may experience yield reductions of up to 0.32 tons/acre (0.72 Mg/ha) for each additional degree of northern latitude. For example, the cultivar Independence is best adapted to USDA plant hardiness zones 5b to 7b and tends to perform poorly outside this range. In colder zones such as 4b, it may experience poor winter survival, resulting in a thin stand or complete stand loss.

Table 1. Forage, conservation, and bioenergy switchgrass cultivars.

Cultivar	Release Year	Ecotype	USDA Zones	Reg. number ^a ; PI number ^b
Forage/Conservation varieties				
Blackwell	1944	Upland	5-7	PI 421520
Caddo	1955	Upland	6-7	PI 476297
Cave-in-Rock	1974	Upland	4-7	PI 469228
Dacotah	1989	Upland	2-4	PI 537588
Forestburg	1989	Upland	3-4	PI 478001
Nebraska 28	1949	Upland	3-4	PI 477003
Pathfinder	1968	Upland	4-5	CV-17; PI 642192
Shawnee	1995	Upland	5-7	CV-181; PI 591824
Shelter	1978	Upland	4-6	PI 430240
Southlow	2001	Upland	4-6	GP-97, PI 642395
Summer	1984	Upland	4-5	CV-258; PI 642191
Sunburst	1998	Upland	3-5	CV-193; PI 598136
Trailblazer	1984	Upland	4-5	CV-146; PI 549094
Bioenergy varieties				
BoMaster	2008	Lowland	6-8	CV-247; PI 645256
Carthage	2006	Upland	4-7	NA
Cedar Creek	2021	Lowland	3-5	CV-290; PI 700113
Cimarron	2008	Lowland	6-9	
Espresso	2023	Lowland	6-9	CV-293; PI 687202
High Tide	2012	Upland	7a	NA
Independence	2021	Lowland	5b-7b	CV-295; PI 704577
Liberty	2014	Lowland	4-6	CV-271; PI 669371
Mt. Airy	N/A	Lowland	5b-7	

^aCultivar/Germplasm registration number; ^bPlant introduction number (<http://www.ars-grin.gov/>). Citations to the relevant cultivar factsheets (where available) are detailed in Appendix 1.

Seed Quality and Seeding Rate

Switchgrass seed should be selected and planted based on two tests:

(i) **Percent Pure Live Seed (PLS) test:**

The Pure Live Seed (PLS) test is a standardized laboratory procedure based on guidelines established by the Association of Official Seed Analysts (AOSA) to evaluate seedlot quality for planting. It measures the **Viable seed percentage**, which reflects the proportion of seeds expected to germinate under ideal conditions, and **Purity**, which represents the proportion of pure seed in the sample by weight (Box 1). AOSA-prescribed germination conditions include a 2-week moist prechill at 41 °F (5 °C) – which may be enhanced with potassium nitrate (KNO₃) to help break dormancy – followed by a 2-week germination phase with alternating temperatures of 59 °F (15 °C) for 16 hours and 86 °F (30 °C) for 8 hours, with light during the warm period. If some seeds fail to germinate, a tetrazolium (TZ) test may be conducted to determine whether these ungerminated seeds are still viable. The TZ test helps provide a more accurate estimate of total seed viability by identifying live but dormant or damaged seeds that did not sprout under standard germination conditions.

Box 1: Calculation of Pure Live Seed (PLS) Percentage

$$PLS (\%) = \frac{\text{Pure seed } (\%) \times \text{Viable seed } (\%)}{100}$$

Where:

- (i) Pure live seed % (Purity) is measured as the ratio of pure seed mass to total seedlot mass and is expressed as a percentage
(*pure seed weight*)/(*seedlot weight*)
- (ii) Total viable seed % is represents the proportion of seeds that are capable of germinating, either immediately or after dormancy is broken (*Germination (%) + Dormant (hard)seed(%)*) or the *Tretrazonium test*)

While the AOSA PLS test offers a standardized assessment of switchgrass seedlot quality, it has limitations under field conditions. It does not account for seedling vigor and may include dormant seeds that germinate in laboratory tests but not in the field. Temperatures during planting at the recommended date, typically around maize planting dates, are too high to break dormancy. Planting them earlier might be too cold to support germination. The PLS methods also require foreknowledge of the number of seeds per lb. Seed tags may not report the number of seeds/lbs, and producers rarely conduct the actual count in practice. The size of switchgrass seeds may vary by more than 40%. Thus, using standard seed values (e.g, ~389,000 seeds/lb (858 seeds/g) in seeding rate calculations (Box 2) may result in inaccurate estimates.

Box 2: Calculation of the seeding rate based on PLS test.

$$\text{Amount of seed (lbs/acre) needed} = \frac{\text{target seeding rate (seeds/ft}^2 \times 43560 \text{ ft}^2/\text{acre)}}{\text{PLS/lb}}$$

- (i) Seeding rate is the PLS rate expressed as a decimal. Recommended rate of successful establishment is 28-37 PLS/ft² (300-400 PLS/m²)

*See Appendix 2 for example calculations

(ii) Seedlot Establishment Tests (SETs - Emergence through 4 cm of sand)

Unlike the PLS, SETs incorporate stress conditions and emergence scenarios to better simulate field conditions. Hence, they provide a more realistic estimate of expected germination rates in the field. Several SETs are available (and may incorporate the AOSA rules), incorporating various stresses before evaluating germination, including the no-prechill, prechill, heat stress, and emergence through a sand medium (2 cm and 4 cm). Viable seeds are estimated based on germinable seeds per gram.

Emergence through 4 cm of sand is considered the most effective SET for predicting field establishment. The procedure is as follows:

1. Place sand in germination trays – plastic flats measuring about 20 in long × 14 in wide × 4 in deep (51 cm × 36 cm × 10 cm). Multiple (up to six) flats should be prepared to ensure statistical reliability.
2. Using an angle-iron tool, make slight furrows in the sand extending the width of the flats.
3. Plant ~0.25 g of seed in the furrows.
4. After planting, cover the seeds with sand drenched with 0.1 oz/gal (1 g/L of H₂O) of Captan⁴ to a depth of 4 cm.
5. Place the flats in a controlled environment set to approximately 68 °F at night and 86 °F between 09:00 h and 16:00 h under natural light. Water daily.
6. Count the number of emerged seedlings **21 days** after planting.
7. The emergence rate can be calculated (Box 3).
8. The seeding rate for field planting is determined based on the actual number of emerged seeds per lb.

Box 3: Calculations of the seeding rate based on SETs

$$\text{Emergence per lb} = \frac{\text{No. of emerged seeds}}{\text{lbs of seeds planted in each flat}}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{Amount of seed (lbs/acre) needed} \\ &= \frac{\text{target seeding rate (seeds/ft}^2 \times 43560 \text{ ft}^2/\text{acre)}}{\text{Emerged no. of seeds/lb}} \end{aligned}$$

⁴Consult herbicide labels, regulations, restrictions, and licensing requirements specific to your state.

Establishment Stage

Switchgrass performs well across a wide range of soil and landscape conditions. Most fields previously used for annual row crops are generally suitable for switchgrass establishment. Productivity is highest on medium- to high-fertility soils that are moderately fine textured, well-drained to moderately well-drained, and have a pH of 5.5 to 7.0.

Figure 1. Switchgrass planting in early May with a John Deere 750 drill.

In the Great Plains and Midwest, the optimal time to plant switchgrass is in the spring, typically from mid-April to early June, ranging from two to three weeks before to two to three weeks after the local corn planting date. When soil moisture and temperature are optimal, switchgrass seedling emergence can begin as early as three days after planting and may be complete within 21 days. However, due to the relatively small seed size compared to annual crops, emergence may be slow, and it is not uncommon for it to appear delayed, with minimal visible growth even 30 days after planting under suboptimal environmental conditions. Due to their small size and panicoid characteristics (subcoleoptile elongation during germination), switchgrass seeds should be planted no deeper than $\frac{1}{4}$ to $\frac{1}{2}$ inch. Planting deeper than $\frac{1}{2}$ inch can lead to poor establishment, as seedlings may fail to emerge and experience delayed adventitious root development.

Switchgrass may be established using either no-till or conventional tillage practices. No-till planting into soybean (*Glycine max*) stubble is highly effective. Therefore, growing soybeans the year prior to switchgrass establishment is highly recommended. Seeding into corn (*Zea mays*) or sorghum (*Sorghum bicolor*) stubble may require residue removal,

disking, and packing to develop a firm seedbed. No-till planting offers several benefits, including soil moisture conservation, reduced erosion, and lower fuel, labor, and time requirements. Another advantage of no-till switchgrass seeding is reduced soil disturbance, which helps minimize erosion and can lower weed pressure. For conventional tillage, the seedbed should be packed firmly – firm enough that walking on it leaves only a faint footprint – to ensure good seed-to-soil contact. Loose, uneven, fluffy, or cloddy seedbeds can result in poor stands or complete establishment failure. A drill equipped with depth bands and closing wheels is best for both no-till and conventionally tilled fields (Fig. 1). Native grass drills, no-till drills, or conventional small grain drills may be used if seeding depth and rate are well-controlled. Grain drills and broadcast seeding are generally ineffective and not recommended.

Evaluation of Establishment Success

Successfully establishing a stand is necessary for a profitable switchgrass

Figure 2. Switchgrass stand counts monitoring early growth under field conditions.

production system. The establishment success is evaluated using a frequency grid, often within 42 to 70 days after planting or when grass seedlings are easy to see and have 3 to 4 leaves. The frequency grid (Fig. 2) is a metal frame or rigid wire mesh containing 25 cells (5 x 5). Each cell measures 6 in x 6 in. To determine seeding success:

1. Place the grid either systematically (for smaller plots) or randomly (for larger plots) within the seeded area and count how many of the 25 cells contain at least 1 seeded plant (presence = 1, absence = 0) (Fig. 3). Switchgrass seedlings can be identified by their

smooth texture and a distinctive purplish coloration on the lower portion of the stem.

2. Flip the grid forward and repeat counts 3 more times at adjacent spots. This gives you 4 placements \times 25 cells = 100 total cells sampled.
3. Sum all cells that had at least 1 seeded plant out of the 100 total cells.
4. The total “Presence” cell count out of 100 total cells is the percent frequency of grass seedlings (Equation 4). For example, a count of 50 is interpreted as a stand of 50%.

Equation 4: Calculating % Seeding Presence

$$\% \text{ seeding presence} = \frac{\text{Number of cells with } \geq 1 \text{ plant}}{100} \times 100$$

$$\text{Density (plants/ft}^2\text{)} = \% \text{ seeding presence} \times 0.04$$

The percent frequency of occurrence can be multiplied by 0.04 to obtain a conservative estimate of plant density/ft². As a general rule, a minimum of four sampling locations per acre should be assessed to obtain a reliable estimate of establishment success.

A stand frequency of 50% or greater (two or more switchgrass plants/ft²) indicates a successful stand, whereas stand frequency between 25 and 50% is marginal to adequate, and stands with less than 25% frequency indicate a partial stand and may need to be reseeded. In a study conducted across five locations in Illinois, Iowa, Nebraska, and South Dakota, switchgrass fields showed a stand frequency of 40% or greater and provided successful stands for bioenergy production.

Figure 3. Frequency grid used to assess switchgrass stand success. Red dots indicate grids with switchgrass seedlings. Good stand (left) with a seedling frequency of 88% (based on four grid placements), and poor stand (right) with a seedling frequency of 28%.

Assessments may need to be conducted at multiple time points during the establishment phase, such as shortly after seedling emergence, at the end of the establishment year, or during spring green-up in the following year. If switchgrass yield declines over consecutive growing seasons or drops by more than 30% from expected levels under favorable conditions and proper management, re-establishment of the stand may be warranted. The goal for the seeding year is to achieve uniform and successful establishment, followed by a post-frost biomass harvest equal to approximately 50% of the cultivar's full yield potential, which is typically achieved by the second to third growing season after planting. Before proceeding, an evaluation of winter survival, soil conditions (including drainage, fertility, and pH), and management practices should be conducted to identify the underlying causes of stand decline.

Common Causes of Poor-Stand Establishment

Several factors can contribute to stand failure in switchgrass, with weed competition – particularly from grassy weeds – being the most common cause. Such competition can delay optimal switchgrass production by one or more years. Other common causes of poor switchgrass stand establishment include:

- Poorly prepared seedbed – Seedbed too loose for good seed-to-soil contact and planting depth control.
- High seed dormancy – Dormant seeds result in uneven germination and establishment across rows.
- Lack of rainfall post-planting – Even when seedlings emerge, prolonged drought can cause seedling mortality.
- Frost heaving – Freeze-thaw cycles can push seedlings out of the soil, exposing roots and leading to desiccation.
- Herbicide damage – Injury to young seedlings from pre- or post-emergent herbicides can reduce stand density or cause seedling death.
- Mowing too closely during the seeding year – Cutting too low can remove the apical meristem, killing young seedlings.

Weed Control in Switchgrass

Figure 4. No-till planting in May 2021 showing herbicide application.

Establishing and maintaining a productive stand of switchgrass requires a clear weed management plan (Fig. 4), especially during the first year. Weeds compete with switchgrass for sunlight, water, and nutrients, potentially leading to reduced stands or complete

establishment failure. Key considerations include site history, soil fertility, planting date, seeding method, and timely herbicide application.

Site History and Herbicide Residue

Before planting, assess prior herbicide use on the site. Residual herbicides from past corn or soybean production may hinder switchgrass establishment. Review product labels for “crop rotation intervals” or “replant periods”.

Field Conditions and Fertility

Wet fields limit spring herbicide application. Apply glyphosate while switchgrass is dormant (early spring or late fall). Avoid fertilization during the first year – high fertility favors fast-growing weeds over young switchgrass seedlings.

Planting Method and Timing

No-till systems reduce weed pressure by minimizing soil disturbance. Delaying planting until after the first flush of weeds allows for a pre-plant glyphosate application. Uniform seeding depth and density also help switchgrass seedlings out-compete weeds.

Weed Management Strategy

Most problematic weeds are grasses like crabgrass, foxtails, barnyardgrass, and johnsongrass. Broadleaf weeds are more easily controlled with selective herbicides. A combination of pre- and post-emergent herbicides is most effective. Table 2 summarizes commonly used herbicides and their recommended application stages in switchgrass systems.

Recommended Herbicides

Note: Herbicide labels, availability, approved uses, and application rules may vary by state; always consult your state's herbicide regulations before use⁵.

Pre-emergent: Atrazine, Simazine, Pendimethalin (only post-establishment)

Post-emergent for grasses: Quinclorac (apply before weeds exceed 4–5 inches)

Broadleaf control: 2,4-D (economical), Aminopyralid, Clopyralid, Fluroxypyr, Dicamba (apply after 3–4 leaf stage in switchgrass)

Table 2. Herbicides used for weed control in switchgrass grown for biofuel production.

Herbicide	Weeds controlled	Stage of application
Glyphosate	Broadleaves and grasses	Burn down before planting or dormant application in spring
Atrazine	Broadleaves some grasses	PRE to weeds and crop
Quinclorac	Broadleaves and annual grasses	PRE or POST when switchgrass is at 3–4 leaf stage
Sulfosulfuron	Broadleaves, sedges, quackgrass	POST when switchgrass is at 3-4 leaf stage
Dicamba	Broadleaves	POST when switchgrass is at 3-4 leaf stage
2,4-D	Broadleaves	POST when switchgrass is at 3-4 leaf stage
Aminopyralid	Broadleaves	POST when switchgrass is at 3-4 leaf stage
Metsulfuron	Broadleaves	POST when switchgrass is at 3-4 leaf stage
Triclopyr	Broadleaves	Established stand Burnonly

⁵Active ingredients are detailed in the Appendix 3

Note: Always read and follow label directions.

Example Year 1 Herbicide Program:

1. Two weeks before planting: 4 lbs a.i./ac glyphosate + 2 lbs a.i./ac 2,4-D
2. Immediately after planting: 1 lbs a.i./ac Atrazine or Simazine + 8 oz a.i./ac Quinclorac
3. Post-emergent (grassy weeds < 5 inches): 8 oz a.i./acre Quinclorac
4. Broadleaf control: 2 lbs a.i./acre 2,4-D at post 3-4 leaf stage

Example for Established Stands:

1. Before green-up: 4 lbs a.i./acre Glyphosate + 2 lbs a.i./acre Atrazine or Simazine
2. For summer annual grasses: 8 oz a.i./acre Quinclorac
3. For broadleaf weeds: 2 lbs a.i./acre 2,4-D

Maintenance Stage

Fertilization

Switchgrass nutrient requirements are much lower than annual row crops like corn. However, nitrogen (N) is the primary nutrient limiting switchgrass yield and persistence. Nitrogen fertilizer application is not recommended during the planting year because N will encourage weed growth, increase

Figure 5. Nitrogen fertilization of switchgrass.

establishment costs, and increase economic risk if the stand fails. Post-establishment year N-management recommendations for switchgrass can be determined based on available soil N, anticipated biomass yield, and the time of switchgrass harvest. N fertilizer should be applied in late spring when the plant begins active growth or when regrowth reaches 6 to 8 inches in height (Fig. 5). Generally, N-fertilizer application rates can be calculated based on N removal by switchgrass biomass. Nitrogen concentration in switchgrass is typically around 1-2% at flowering but may decline to as low as 0.5% after a killing frost due to translocation of N to below-ground organs for overwinter storage. Consequently, if switchgrass is harvested after a killing frost and yields 4.5-5 tons/acre (10-11 Mg/ha) of dry biomass with a crude protein concentration of 4% (equivalent to approximately 0.64% N), the estimated N removal is about 45-50 lb N/acre (50-55 kg N/ha). Based on regional guidelines for the Great Plains and Midwest, a general N fertilizer recommendation is 10-15 lb N/acre (5-7 kg N/ha) per ton of anticipated biomass yield when harvesting occurs after a killing frost. The N application rate should be adjusted according to soil N levels and estimated N mineralization rates, as determined through soil testing. In newly established switchgrass fields with high

residual soil N, fertilizer application rates can be significantly reduced during the initial years of production. However, insufficient N inputs over time can lead to a decline in biomass yield, stand vigor, and increased weed pressure. Long-term yield sustainability requires maintaining adequate N levels through appropriately timed and calibrated fertilization strategies. In Illinois, Iowa, and Nebraska, the yields of bioenergy switchgrass cultivars ‘Independence’ and ‘Liberty’ increased with rising N application rates, with optimal yields achieved at 50 lb N/acre. Similarly, in South Dakota, the bioenergy cultivar ‘Carthage’ also reached optimal yields at 50 lb N/acre (~56 kg N/ha).

If soil pH is less than 5.0, lime should be applied to raise pH to 6.5 to allow for more efficient utilization of soil nutrients. Adequate levels of phosphorus (P) and potassium (K) will be in the soil profile in most agricultural fields in the Midwest and Great Plains. If warranted by soil tests, P and K should be applied before planting and incorporated into the soil to promote root growth and encourage rapid establishment. The P and K removal rates can vary considerably and are dependent on growing season, yield, timing of harvest, precipitation, and soil quality. One ton of switchgrass removes about 4 lbs P/acre (~4.5 kg/ha) and 40 lbs K/acre (~45 kg/ha).

Nutrients removed through biomass harvest will need to be replenished through appropriate fertilization based on soil test recommendations. Comprehensive soil testing should be conducted the year prior to planting to address any major nutrient deficiencies or soil pH imbalances. Particular attention should be given to phosphorus (P) levels, as P is essential for early root development and seedling establishment. Given the deep-rooted nature of switchgrass, soil samples should be collected in 1-ft increments to a depth of 5 ft to accurately assess nutrient availability throughout the rooting zone.

Diseases and Pest Management

Currently, there are no major diseases or insect pests that have caused significant economic damage to switchgrass. However, as the scale of switchgrass cultivation increases, it is important to routinely monitor fields for potential pest and disease issues. Early detection through regular scouting can help prevent emerging threats from becoming economically significant.

Harvesting Stage

Harvest Timing and Cutting Height

Early harvesting at around canopy closure (Fig. 6) or the heading stage (Fig. 7) is generally discouraged for bioenergy feedstock production.

Figure 6. Switchgrass canopy closure in June.

Figure 7. Fully headed Liberty switchgrass in mid-August.

Switchgrass biomass should be harvested once per year after a killing frost (Fig. 8). Harvesting switchgrass several weeks after a killing frost or visible senescence helps improve both plant health and biomass quality. This delay allows N and other nutrients to move from the aboveground parts into the roots, where they are stored for winter and used for new growth in spring. It also reduces moisture, nitrogen, and ash content in the biomass, improving feedstock quality for combustion and other uses. However, harvest should not be delayed too long, as lodged plants can lead to biomass losses and make harvesting less efficient.

Figure 6. Switchgrass after the killing frost in October near Ames, Iowa.

The recommended cutting height for switchgrass is 4 inches (Fig. 9). In northern regions, a higher stubble height of around 6 inches may help reduce the risk of winter injury.

Figure 7. Harvesting switchgrass at 4 inch stubble height at Madrid, Iowa.

Moisture Content and Drying

Proper moisture management is critical for safe and efficient storage. Switchgrass should be baled when the plant moisture content is below 20%. Moisture targets for round bales should be 18% or lower, while large rectangular bales should be baled at 16% or lower. Baling at higher moisture levels increases the risk of mold development during storage, which can lead to spoilage and introduce inhibitors that interfere with biomass conversion processes. Additionally, high-moisture bales are heavier, leading to increased transportation costs.

Field drying can be used for moisture reduction and is often achieved with self-propelled mower-conditioners (swathers) with rotary heads. These machines crush plant stems to facilitate moisture loss while maintaining the structural integrity of the biomass and consolidating it into windrows. In regions where timely drying is difficult due to weather, balers can be fitted with preservative applicators that spray compounds such as propionic acid to reduce microbial growth in bales with higher moisture.

Baling

Harvest operations begin with swathing or mowing/conditioning, then raking, baling, road-siding, and finally transport to a storage or conversion facility (Fig. 10-13).

Figure 10. Switchgrass swathing near South Shore, South Dakota.

Figure 11. Switchgrass round-baling near Ithaca, Nebraska.

Figure 9. Gathering round-baled switchgrass near Ithaca, Nebraska.

Figure 8. Switchgrass rectangular baling at Urbana, Illinois.

Switchgrass can be baled using either round (Fig. 11 and Fig. 12) or large rectangular balers (Fig. 13). Round balers produce cylindrical bales that typically range from 1.2 to 1.8 meters in both diameter and length. Large rectangular balers are usually 0.9 to 1.2 meters in height and width and 1.8 to 2.4 meters in length.

Rectangular bales are convenient to stack and transport, whereas round bales are more resistant to water penetration and can withstand constant handling. Round balers are less expensive — approximately one-quarter to one-third the cost of large rectangular balers — but they have lower field efficiency due to the need to stop and wrap each bale. Large rectangular balers offer continuous operation, higher capacity, and greater efficiency in loading and transport, but they are more expensive and produce bales that are more vulnerable to moisture damage when stored outdoors. Alternatively, after raking, a forage chopper can be used to chop the switchgrass to a loose, non-compacted material, which is subsequently baled and transported in bales to a storage or conversion facility (Fig. 14-15).

Figure 10. Forage chopping windrows into forage wagon.

Figure 11. Baling chopped windrows using Orkel baler.

Storage

Most storage occurs on field edges or satellite storage facilities, either outdoors or indoors. When stored outside, bales should be placed on well-drained surfaces such as gravel or crushed rock to minimize moisture absorption from the ground. Wrapping round bales with plastic netting rather than twine significantly reduces dry matter. Tarping and stacking

methods should prevent water infiltration, as exposure to precipitation can severely degrade biomass quality. Indoor storage offers the highest level of protection, typically resulting in dry matter losses of no more than 2%, compared to losses of up to 13% for outdoor tarped bales and as high as 25% for bales stored uncovered in the open. Bales stored directly on the ground are particularly susceptible to spoilage due to moisture infiltration from the soil. In contrast, using gravel bases or elevated platforms significantly reduces this risk. Typically, degradation is confined to the outer layers of the bale, while the inner core remains largely preserved.

In regions with high humidity or frequent rainfall, wet storage is a viable alternative. Chopped switchgrass with moisture content above 40% is stored in silage pits or plastic-wrapped stacks. This method minimizes harvest losses and enhances conversion efficiency but demands specialized equipment and entails higher costs. Due to low bulk density, densification may also be necessary to improve transport efficiency. Loafer stackers offer another option, forming dome-shaped stacks that shed water. While less efficient than baling, this method can be cost-effective in dry regions.

Potential Yield

Switchgrass biomass yields can vary based on the production region, cultivars grown, site productivity, precipitation, and management. New bioenergy-type cultivars establish faster and reach peak yields faster. Generally, it takes two growing years for switchgrass to produce optimum yields. In the establishment year, a stand with good weed management and ample rainfall should produce about half of the fully established yield potential of the site and cultivar. The establishment year should be dedicated to successful stand establishment and proper weed control. It is feasible to produce 30-50% of the yield potential and harvest after killing

frost in the planting year, and 70-100% of the yield potential by the end of the second year after planting. Fields should be at full production potential by the second or third growing season after planting, depending on rainfall, and should be productive for a decade or more. A long-term study in Nebraska has maintained full production for 25 years with good management. In large-scale switchgrass fields in Illinois, Iowa, Nebraska, and South Dakota, we have observed average biomass yields exceeding 5 tons/acre/year beginning the year after planting.

Switchgrass Production Cost

An economic study from Illinois shows that switchgrass is a profitable option for landowners with marginal lands. With a dry matter yield of 4.7 tons/acre (10.45 Mg/ha), switchgrass can economically compete with soybeans priced at \$80/ton (\$88/Mg), and in some locations, with corn at \$60/ton (\$66/Mg). Production costs vary by region and management but generally fall into three categories: establishment, maintenance, and harvest. Establishment costs include land preparation, seeding, and drilling; maintenance involves herbicides, N fertilizer, and application; while harvest costs cover swathing, raking, and baling. Tillage costs apply only in the establishment year and are eliminated under no-till systems. Herbicide costs are typically limited to the first two years, while N fertilizer is applied starting in year two, with costs dependent on the source and rate. Machinery expenses are influenced by equipment type, labor and fuel prices, field size, and location. Baling costs, usually charged per bale, are generally lower for round bales than square bales and tend to rise with increased biomass.

A recent five-year techno-economic analysis across Illinois, Iowa, Nebraska, and South Dakota confirmed the economic advantage of improved bioenergy cultivars (Independence, Liberty and Carthage) over

the traditional forage types. In Illinois, the Independence cultivar fertilized with 50 lb N/acre (56 kg N/ha) had an average production cost of ~\$138/acre/year (\$340/ha/year) and yielded the highest profit margin of ~\$156/acre/year (\$385/ha/year), especially in USDA Plant Hardiness Zone (PHZ) 6a (Urbana, IL). In Iowa, Liberty under the same N rate showed a production cost of ~\$119/acre/yr (\$294/ha/year) and a profit margin of ~\$142/acre/year (\$350/ha/year), particularly in PHZ 5b (Madrid, IA, and Ithaca, NE). These trends suggest the broader applicability of cultivar-specific profitability across similar climatic zones.

Environmental and Ecosystem Services

There are numerous environmental benefits to growing switchgrass. The perennial root system of switchgrass provides three important ecosystem services: protecting soil from wind and water erosion by stabilizing fragile soils, intercepting nutrients, thereby reducing nitrate-N leaching, and sequestering C in the soil profile. Switchgrass contributes to carbon sequestration by storing carbon in the soil profile. The rate of soil C accumulation has been estimated at an average of 1.01 Mg C/ha/year, with values reaching up to 2.8 Mg C/ha/year. However, short-term increases in soil carbon are difficult to detect, as measurable changes typically occur over longer timescales. In contrast, belowground biomass offers a more immediate and promising pathway for demonstrating carbon sequestration benefits in the short to near term. Belowground (root) biomass C can accumulate up to 1.75-2 Mg/C/ha/yr within four years of cultivation. Unlike annual crops, switchgrass develops deep root systems that can reach depths of up to 3 meters, facilitating long-term carbon storage in subsoil layers where carbon is less prone to microbial decomposition and loss.

A recent study in Illinois revealed that soil N₂O emissions were two times lower in switchgrass plots than corn plots. Switchgrass cultivation also enhances soil water quality by reducing nitrate leaching into groundwater. While nitrate losses under switchgrass are initially comparable to corn during the establishment year, they decline significantly over time (at least 80% within three years) as the stand matures and root systems extend deeper into the soil profile, improving nutrient interception and retention.

Switchgrass cultivation also contributes to enhanced wildlife habitat quality. In particular, switchgrass fields provide critical breeding and foraging grounds for birds and pollinators during the spring and summer seasons. Findings from our five-year, field-scale trials in Illinois demonstrate that bioenergy switchgrass cultivars can support grassland bird populations, help replace lost habitats, and aid in the recovery of vulnerable species. Species such as the Common Yellowthroat, Dickcissel, Grasshopper Sparrow, and Sedge Wren were observed more frequently in switchgrass plots than in adjacent corn fields. In addition, insect diversity was significantly higher in switchgrass fields compared to continuous corn fields at two Illinois locations (Fig. 16). Four major insect pollinator orders – Hymenoptera (bees), Diptera (flies), Coleoptera (beetles), and Lepidoptera (butterflies and moths) – were present at both sites, indicating that switchgrass can support a robust pollinator community.

Figure 12. Acoustic monitor in switchgrass plot at Brighton, IL in June 2020 (a). Sample spectrograms of bird vocalizations recorded (b). Adult male indigo bunting (c) and red-winged blackbird (d), in switchgrass fields in June 2021.

To protect nesting birds, management activities such as fertilization and weed control should be minimized during mid to late summer, allowing time for fledglings to become mobile and independent. Harvest timing should also align with wildlife conservation goals. Delaying harvest until after a killing frost helps safeguard grassland-nesting species that depend on switchgrass fields during the spring and summer. In addition, producers may consider partial harvesting or leaving uncut strips to provide dense cover for overwintering wildlife and suitable nesting habitat the following spring.

Outlook and Policy Implications

Current research demonstrates that switchgrass is a high-yielding, environmentally protective, and economically viable bioenergy crop. Its long-term success depends on the availability of suitable agricultural land and the profitability it offers to farmers. With established best management practices and improved cultivars, sustainable biomass production can benefit both producers and biorefineries. However, limited adoption to date is largely due to inefficiencies in biomass conversion technologies, farmers' reluctance to plant switchgrass without

a secure market, and biorefineries' hesitance to invest without a reliable feedstock supply. To overcome these barriers, policy interventions should offer incentives that reflect both the energy value and environmental services provided by switchgrass, while also fostering the development of stable, long-term feedstock supply chains. Importantly, payments for ecosystem services – such as carbon sequestration, water quality protection, and wildlife habitat enhancement – can further improve the economic attractiveness of switchgrass, compensating farmers for the broader public benefits their land stewardship provides.

Appendices

Appendix 1: Cultivar factsheets and registration information.

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Appendix 2: Calculating seed amounts on a Pure Live Seed (PLS) basis

<u>Grass 1</u>	<u>Grass 2</u>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pure seed = 97.25% • Germination = 90% • Dormant seed = 3% • $PLS\% = (97.25 \times 93) / 100 = 90.44$ • Typical seeding rate = 10 to 12 lbs PLS/acre • To plant 10 lbs PLS/acre must sow about 11 lbs bulk seed ($10 / 0.9044$) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pure seed = 82.3% • Germination = 64% • Dormant seed = 10% • $PLS\% = (82.3 \times 74) / 100 = 60.9$ • Typical seeding rate = 5 to 8 lbs PLS/acre • To plant 7 lbs PLS/acre must sow about 11.5 lbs bulk seed ($7 / 0.609$)

Appendix 3: Herbicides used in switchgrass production, and their active ingredients

Herbicide*	Active Ingredient
Glyphosate	2-(phosphonomethylamino)acetic acid
Atrazine	6-chloro-4- <i>N</i> -ethyl-2- <i>N</i> -propan-2-yl-1,3,5-triazine-2,4-diamine
Quinclorac	3,7-dichloroquinoline-8-carboxylic acid
Sulfosulfuron	1-(4,6-dimethoxypyrimidin-2-yl)-3-(2-ethylsulfonylimidazo[1,2- <i>a</i>]pyridin-3-yl)sulfonylurea
Dicamba	3,6-dichloro-2-methoxybenzoic acid
2,4-D	2-(2,4-dichlorophenoxy) acetic acid
Aminopyralid	4-amino-3,6-dichloropyridine-2-carboxylic acid
Metsulfuron	2-[(4-methoxy-6-methyl-1,3,5-triazin-2-yl)carbamoylsulfamoyl]benzoic acid
Triclopyr	2-(3,5,6-trichloropyridin-2-yl)oxyacetic acid
Simazine	6-chloro-2- <i>N</i> ,4- <i>N</i> -diethyl-1,3,5-triazine-2,4-diamine
Pendimethalin	3,4-dimethyl-2,6-dinitro- <i>N</i> -pentan-3-ylaniline
Clopyralid	3,6-dichloropyridine-2-carboxylic acid
Fluroxypyr	2-(4-amino-3,5-dichloro-6-fluoropyridin-2-yl)oxyacetic acid

*Herbicide labels, availability, approved uses, and application rules may vary by state; always consult your state's herbicide regulations before use.

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